

Repercussions of Ritual Dances to Personal Adjustment: A Perspicacious Study Among School Children

Authors : Abdul Rahiman Kannam Kulam

Abstract : Reflecting the concepts of the development of the whole child, it is claimed that, purposeful engagement in physical activities or exercise involved ritual dances has the potential to engender in young people, the purpose of the present study was to analyze school children and their personal adjustment based on Ritual dance participation. For the purpose, two thousand and three hundred school children of Kerala were analyzed. AISS manual of A.K.P Sinha and R.P Singh was used to collect the data for adjustments. The adjustment qualities classifies as excellent, good, average, unsatisfactory and very unsatisfactory. The total performance denotes the state of adjustment based on the classifications. Findings of the study were subjected to percentages and 't' ratio. The study enlightened that, the emotional, social and overall adjustments are better than non-athletes. But the study elucidated that, there is no difference in educational adjustment of school athletes and non athletes among school children.

Keywords : ritual dances, emotional adjustment, Poorakkali, Kolkkali, Margamkali

Conference Title : ICSEHS 2014 : International Conference on Sport, Exercise and Health Sciences

Conference Location : Bangkok, Thailand

Conference Dates : December 24-25, 2014